
The Impact of Necropolitics in International Relations (A Case Study From Gaza to Kyiv)

Jajnadatta Pattanayak

Research Scholar, P.G. Department of Political Science, Berhampur University, Ganjam Odisha

Mail: jajnadattapattanayak700@gmail.com

Sujata Sahoo

Student, P.G. Department of Political Science, Berhampur University, Ganjam, Odisha

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17129764>

ARTICLE DETAILS

Research Paper

Accepted: 20-08-2025

Published: 10-09-2025

Keywords:

*History, Geopolitics,
Necropolitics, Riviera,
Jingoistic.*

ABSTRACT

Every man and state must learn from their own history, but why does the learning remain in halfway? An eminent popular thinker, Karl Marx, rightly stated that, "History repeats itself, first as tragedy, second as farce." Yes, history repeats itself, and we are witnessing the impact of plate tectonics in geopolitics from Ukraine to Palestine in a rampant manner. This study will showcase how necropolises deeply affect the backbones of both Palestine and Ukraine." As a result, Gaza is on the way to becoming the Riviera in the Middle East, and it can only be possible through mass killing and genocide. In contrast, Ukraine, once called the breadbasket of Europe, is also on the brink of collapse due to ongoing wars, and people are suffering from an insufficiency of food, fertilizer, and fuel, while civilian properties and hospitals are also under attack. So, this analysis will focus on the central cause and effect. In a jingoistic political phenomenon, the role and behavior of nation-states, warmongering attitude changed the course of contemporary international relations. In the first half of the 21st century (2001-2050), it seems to be the toughest era ever perceived. This topic will examine the ongoing war and its implications, particularly through case studies from Gaza to Ukraine.

Introduction

The word Necropolitics signifies ‘the politics of death’, which has a very grey shape in front of the world community. Meanwhile, ‘Necro’ relates to ‘a corpse or death’ & somehow politics as usual, the ‘day-to-day state of affairs’. Cameroonian historian Achille Mbembe coined the term in an essay published in 2003. But now the word has got more momentum, because nations are using this dark politics (Nai, 2023) described in a book ‘Dark Politics: The Personality of Politicians and the Future of Democracy’ which highlights the evil side of a particular nation, at a specific period of time. Over the last century, many wars have been fought, and significantly, the curse of the First and Second World Wars changed the global scenario for a long time. The world is drifting towards the Third World War, which will eventually take place if everything continues in this same manner. Albert Einstein said, “It is often quoted as having said: ‘I know not with what weapons World War III will be fought, but World War IV will be fought with sticks and stones. It is clearly visible in the contemporary geopolitical scenario, particularly in Gaza and Ukraine.

Statism, Self-Help, and Survival

Necropolitics, the idea is more realistic than philosophical in practice, for the survival of countries worldwide. Here we can say, “Freedom for the pike is the death of minnows”. One has to die for the survival of others. This is happening in an international phenomenon. What the nation state does with small, underdeveloped peripheral countries is evident. According to Kenneth Waltz, the popular international neo-realist, the global world order is chaotic and anarchical. They are struggling for survival, self-help, and statism, which cannot be ignored. The rise of superpower rivalry, primarily among so-called superpowers, disrupts the geopolitical world order. International politics, which is based on liberal philosophy, has become value-neutral due to rising mutual mistrust among the nation-states. In the matter of Ukraine or Palestine, both are struggling to safeguard their national sovereignty due to ongoing conflicts with their neighboring states. It’s like a rare event where the aggressor countries and their leaders are charged with the arrest warrants issued by the International Criminal Court (ICC). The arrest warrants were issued against Benjamin Netanyahu and Vladimir Putin for the allegations of genocide and war crimes.

Genesis and Growth of Conflicts

Initially, the genesis of the crisis or conflict in Palestine can also be traced back to the Sykes-Picot agreement and the Balfour declarations. First, the Sykes-Picot agreement, signed in 1916 between the

United Kingdom and France, talked about a specified recognition of an independent Arab state or confederation of Arab states; otherwise, this agreement disregarded any previous arrangements for a Jewish homeland in Palestine. Second, signed in 1917, was known as the Balfour Declaration, which gave the opportunity and a formal understanding between the Jewish community and the United Kingdom leadership to create a separate land for Jews. It's undeniable that European powers and their colonial tenancies more or less ruined the international structure. In the case of Israel-Palestine and India-Pakistan, the Occupation of Diego Garcia and control over the Falkland Islands are the most prominent examples. After the creation of Israel as an independent nation state in the middle of the distinct religious-ethnic neighbors, supposedly, this is a kind of ambiguous situation where enemy countries surround the state of Israel, with its creation in 1948, during the same time, a war was waged between Palestine and Israel. It was the first time that the United Nations Peacekeeping forces (Blue Helmets) were deployed and declared a green zone in the border areas of both countries. Even after many peace negotiations, the conflicts and deaths have not stopped yet. The Armistice agreement (1949) established short-term peace, but the peace never occurred. Israel and other West Asian Countries fought with each other in 1967, known as the Six-Day War, then after the Yom Kippur War (1973), the Lebanese War (2006), and now the Hamas-Israeli Conflict (2023) respectively. What is happening is that only death tolls are rising, necropolitics is real, and it's happening every day. Recently, in the near future, the IDF (Israeli Defense Forces) occupied the Golan Heights; at the same time, the West Bank is in turmoil, and nobody knows what will be next.

Every conflict has a long and unending history; Ukraine has its own, which can be treated based on the internal colonialism during the USSR. Ukraine was liberated from the USSR in December 1991 through a referendum, which an overwhelming majority of voters endorsed. Since its independence, it has been under the supervision and influence of many leaders; simultaneously, the West sees it as an opportunity to contain the Russian Federation. The intention to expand NATO by the inclusion of Ukraine began in 2002 during the Bucharest summit, which further fueled mutual mistrust and antagonism between Russia and Ukraine. Russians waged a war against Ukraine and occupied the Crimean Peninsula in 2014. The reason is self-evident, because according to NATO principles, no country can become an active and permanent member if it has a disputed border with any other country. Even after the ousting of Russian-backed leader Victor Yanukovich (2014) in Ukraine, after a pro-democratic coup, when actor cum President Mr. Volodymyr Zelensky came to power showed more interest in joining NATO, which could be one of the reasons for the recent conflict.

The Riviera in Stalemate

The UN estimated that more than 1,300 Palestinians have been killed at food centers since May 2025. Despite mounting international outrage and allegations of war crimes, and Hamas's acceptance of the latest ceasefire proposal put forward by Qatar and Egypt, Israel has intensified attacks on Gaza City in preparation for a new offensive. What is unfolding now in Gaza goes far beyond Israel's stated aims of defeating Hamas and releasing Hamas's prisoners. The growing conflict of evidence points to an intent to destroy Palestinian life and society in Gaza itself. The most brutal of crimes are being committed against 2.3 million people — in full view of the world. Israel cannot continue devastating Gaza any further. In recent years, the collective West, including European powers and the USA, seems to be more worried about Ukraine rather than Gaza or the Palestinian people as a whole. Since the formation of Israel in 1948, the Middle East has been like a boiling pot. The Palestine Question and its problems seem to be unresolved nowadays. The UN said that the death toll has just approximately surpassed 56000 and added that nearly 18000 children have died throughout this war. It's a new normal situation because it happens daily, but all the so-called superpowers and alternative power centers are silent on this issue. In contrast, Israel is backed by Western powers, and they want to make Gaza the Riviera of West Asia, which is very much imaginary cum philosophical in nature. Notwithstanding, some of the Western allies, like Australia, Canada, France, and the UK, have started speaking and criticizing the Israeli atrocities, because they are doing mass killing, which can be called genocide. So here we can say the momentum of the Palestinian state got its moments, but the question here is, at what cost? As of now, out of 193 countries, 147 nation-states accepted the existence of Palestine; otherwise, 90 countries showed their interest in supporting the two-state solution. Power imbalance and power vacuum are the backbone of Palestine in general and Gaza in particular. In case of a power vacuum after the ouster of Bashar al-Assad in Syria, American strikes over the Iranian nuclear facilities, and Russian involvement in the Ukrainian conflict created a sense of power imbalances in this region. Now, Palestine is divided into many parts, such as the West Bank, the Gaza Strip, Jerusalem, etc. The time has come for the international responsible actors to solve this matter as quickly as possible. International organizations like the UN must take proactive steps to galvanize that issue.

Breadbasket with no bread

Ukraine, once called the breadbasket of Europe, produces a considerable portion of food grains, mainly wheat, feeding a large portion of the population worldwide. However, after the special military operation in Ukraine carried out by the Russian Federation on 25 February 2022, the food supply chain and food

security have completely halted. War and confrontations between two neighboring countries directly disrupt the just international world order. Most of the areas, basically eastern parts of Ukraine, such as Donetsk, Luhansk, Zaporizhzhia, and Kharkiv, are now under the occupation of the Russian Army. Even the International Criminal Court issued an arrest warrant, but at the same time, they are undermining it. The endgame is undefined, the ceasefire is far away, mass killing is underway, and territorial sovereignty is in threat between Russia and Ukraine. Here, food, fertilizers, and fuel are somehow derailed because of security issues, halting due to war, prices fluctuating, and fertilizers, which are too necessary for the farmers, cannot be transported.

Where does India stand?

As India's Prime Minister stated, 'This is not the era of war', which ultimately symbolizes the real stance of India in this changing international politics. Where India promotes the idea of *Viswa Mitra*, it's tough to strike a balance between the two warring countries. In the case of the Middle East or Palestine-Israel conflict, India's stance remains the same. It believes in the two-nation theory, which recognizes both and respects their territorial sovereignty. Initially, India stood for the creation of a full-fledged Palestine. But now, it believes in the two-nation theory due to India's interdependence and deep engagement with Israel; otherwise, Israel remains a reliable partner over time. Both countries share cordial relations with India, and Ukraine and Russia have good relations. Even during the ongoing crisis, the Indian Prime Minister travelled to both those countries. India can go to either country in an interdependent world where no one can survive in isolation. Even most Indian students studying in Ukraine have successfully evacuated with zero casualties and no injuries through an evacuation operation known as 'Operation Ganga'. So, what about Russia? Today, the relationship is like a time-tested one, evolving with ups and downs. On the contrary, it's too hard to handle this situation, in which the whole Western world is putting pressure on India not to buy anything from Russia, but the demand and requirement are to avoid these pressures. So, both countries should make every effort as quickly as possible to create a more peaceful world through diplomacy and peace agreements.

Way forward

In jingoistic international relations, the death politics is undermined and compromised. Real peace is absent due to the warmongering attitude of the nation-states. In the case study and the problems of Palestine to Ukraine, the question of human rights became irrelevant, as realism-moral aspiration is inapplicable; that's why the whole international system seems anarchical in nature—the cut-throat

competition among their power centers to safeguard their national interest and strategic autonomy. Gaza is dying, and recently, Israel passed a bill to gain complete control over it. Here is a question: why is the international organization silent, and why are the so-called superpowers silent? A small civil society group, Nihon Hidankyo, based in Japan, got the Nobel Peace Prize for avoiding nuclear warheads in the future to achieve disarmament. At the same time, countries' roles are declining to accomplish a better world order. So global efforts have to be made immediately for a just world order, to stop the genocide in both Gaza and Ukraine. Peace is the last resort and end goal—war-fighting steps to be taken by the world community, the countries, organizations, and leaders.

Conclusion

Leaders of the world and international organizations should make diplomatic efforts to end the conflicts in Gaza and Ukraine on a war footing. Meanwhile, UN agencies have collectively and consistently highlighted the extreme urgency of delivering immediate and full-scale humanitarian aid given the escalating hunger-related deaths, rapidly worsening levels of acute malnutrition, and plummeting levels of Food consumption in Gaza, where hundreds of thousands go days without anything to eat. On the other hand, Russia's threat against Ukraine continued to cause immense civilian suffering. Since its full-scale invasion in February 2022, Russian forces have committed widespread war crimes and other abuses and maintained a climate of fear in Russia-occupied areas of Ukraine. Leaders are silent and not serious about real peace. But efforts continue, more or less by the different entities, maybe it's like a 'tip of the iceberg', but hopefully the so-called death politics cum necropolitics must come to an end.

References

1. Al Jazeera English. (2023, October 15). Israel-Palestine: 'The first victim in war is the truth' [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GEBqvMEFExY>.
2. Al-Haq. (2023, November 2). Palestinian Civil Society Organisations Call on the UN Commission of Inquiry to condemn Israel's ongoing war crimes, crimes against humanity and intent to commit genocide in Gaza. <https://www.alhaq.org/advocacy/22063.html>
3. Amnesty International (2019). Israel and Occupied Palestinian Territories: Destination: Occupation digital tourism and Israel's illegal settlements in the Occupied Palestinian Territories. <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/mde15/9490/2019/en/>.

4. Center for Preventive Action (2023). "Israeli-Palestinian conflict." Council on Foreign Relations. <https://www.cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker/conflict/israeli-palestinian-conflict>.
5. The Guardian (2023, November 16). "Israel and Palestine: A complete guide to the crisis." The Guardian. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2023/nov/03/israel-and-palestine-a-complete-guide-to-the-crisis>.
6. United Nations Relief and Works Agency for Palestine Refugees in the Near East (UNRWA) (2023). "Gaza_15 years of blockade." UNRWA. <https://www.unrwa.org/gaza15-years-blockade>.
7. Sharma, P. (2023, October 14). Israel-Palestine war: A simple history of how it all began |Explained Gravitas Plus [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0anQIEeLonA>.